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Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

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Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumar@gmail.com

Managing Editor

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Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

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jichelnu@gmail.com

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Concept of Ātman in Ayurveda and Tarkaśāstra

Dr. Devan E. M¹

Introduction

The Vedas are the world's oldest extant literary texts. They are regarded as the foundation of the Indian knowledge system. According to the Indian Knowledge system, there are fourteen vidyas, or branches of knowledge. They are four vedas, six vedaṅgas, Mīmāṃsa, Nyāyavistara, Purāṇas and Dharmaśāstra². According to certain experts, there are Eighteen branches including four Upavedas i.e., Ayurveda, Dhanurveda, Arthaśāstra and Gandharvaveda³. There are different opinions among scholars on the inclusion of Arthaśāstra as Upaveda. Some of them accept Sthāpatya Veda or Śilpaveda as upaveda instead of Arthaśāstra. Sages shared their thoughts and beliefs on the material world and the eternal world in these branches of the Indian knowledge system. The emancipation from the cycle of rebirth and death, known as Mokṣa, was considered the ultimate aim of life by the rīṣis of ancient India. So, through their works and counsel, they explain and demonstrate the route to liberation. The liberation of the Ātman from the shackles of this world is the idea of Mokṣa. They elaborate on the soul's nature and attributes in their writings. Different systems have different views on the soul. While some claim it is Nirguṇa, or without any attributes, others think it is Saguṇa. While others recognise both the Supreme and Individual Soul, some solely accept the Supreme Soul. Thus, there are several inconsistencies among diverse systems' conceptions of the soul. In this study, I want to contrast several points of view about Soul in Ayurveda and Nyāya Philosophy.

Derivation and Definition of Ātman

Ātma is one among the nine substances in Tarka śāstra.⁴ The term 'आत्मा' is derived from the root 'अत'. The meaning of 'अत' is

1 Ass istant professor, emdevanem@gma il.com, 8848382561

2 अङ्गानि वेदाश्चत्वारो मीमांसा न्यायविस्तरः । पुराणं धर्मशास्त्रं च विद्याहोताश्चतुर्दश ॥ (पु.सा)

3 आयुर्वेदो धनुर्वेदो गान्धर्वश्चैव ते त्रयः । अर्थशास्त्रं चतुर्थन्तु विद्याह्याष्टादशैव ताः ॥ (वि.पु.3.6.29)

4 तत्र द्रव्याणि पृथ्व्यप्तेजोवाय्वाकाशकालदिगात्ममनांसि नवैव (त.सं.)

‘सातत्य गमने’ which means ‘*that which has continuous motion always*’. Hence the Nirukti of the word ātma is ‘*the one which spread all over*’.⁵ Tarka śāstra defines ātman as ज्ञानाधिकरणमात्मा. The substratum of knowledge is ātman. According to Tarka śāstra, knowledge is the property of both jīvātma and paramĀtma. Hence, ज्ञानाधिकरणम् is the common definition of jīvātman and paramātma. The knowledge residing in paramĀtma is eternal. Therefore, the specific definition of paramātma is नित्यज्ञानाधिकरणम्. The specific definition of jīvātman is सुखाद्यधिकरणम् I सुखादि means the properties सुखम्, दुःखम्, इच्छा, द्वेषः, प्रयत्नः, धर्मः, अधर्मः, संस्कारः (भावना), which are residing only in jīvātman not in paramātman. Hence the specific definition of jīvātma is सुखाद्यधिकरणम् I

Classification of Ātma

Tarka śāstra classified ātman as -

- absolute soul (परमात्मा)
- empirical soul (जीवात्मा)

Paramātma is Īśwara (god), who is omniscient (सर्वज्ञ) and is singular (एक). Each living body has one jīvātma. Hence empirical souls are many. The empirical soul is also eternal and omnipresent.⁶

The concept of Ātman in Ayurveda

The concept of Ātma in Ayurveda, vaiśeṣika and sāṅkhya philosophies are almost similar. In Ayurveda the term indicating the ātman is Puruṣa which is the same as Sāṅkhya darśana. The term puruṣa is derived from the root ‘पुर’. it is the one who resides in the body.⁷ In Ayurveda it is one of the components of life, the other three being sarīra, indriya and manas. In other words, it is one of the three components of a living person.⁸

Synonyms of Ātma in Ayurveda

According to caraka, अव्यक्तं, आत्मा, क्षेत्रज्ञः, शाश्वतः, विभु, अव्ययः these are the synonyms of Ātma.⁹ अव्यक्तं – unmanifested, आत्मा – which always travels, क्षेत्रज्ञः - knower of the body, शाश्वतः- the eternal, विभुः - the ever pervading, अव्ययः- the one without change.

Classification of Ātma in Ayurveda

Ayurveda in lines with Vaiśeṣika philosophy and Tarka śāstra holds that there are two types of souls

- 1) jīvātman (The individual soul/empirical soul)
- 2) Paramātman (The absolute soul)

jīvātma (The individual soul/empirical soul)

Ayurveda considers that the empirical soul is perishable as it

5 ‘अतति = सकलं व्याप्नोति इति आत्मा’

6 स द्विविधः परमात्मा जीवात्मा च । तल ईश्वरः सर्वज्ञः परमात्मा एक एव । जीवात्मा प्रतिशरीरं भिन्नो विभुर्नित्यश्च । (त.सं.)

7 पुरि शरीरे शेते इति पुरुषः

8 शरीरेन्द्रियसत्त्वात्मसंयोगे धारि जीवितम् । नित्यगश्चानुबन्धश्च पर्यायैरायुरुच्यते ॥ (च.सू.1/42)

9 अव्यक्तमात्मा क्षेत्रज्ञः शाश्वतो विभुरव्ययः (च.शा.१.६१)

is generated from causes. Anything with a cause is not eternal.¹⁰ jīvātman co-exists with mind and body. It is eternal and omnipresent. The empirical soul is termed as *Samyoga Puruṣa* (conjugated person) because it is the soul which conjugates with mind and body. In Ayurveda the terms *Karma puruṣa*, *Shad dhātuja puruṣa*, *Chikitsā puruṣa* denote jīvātman. The eight guṇas *sukha*, *dukha*, *icha* etc are residing in jīvātma.

Paramātma (absolute soul)

The absolute soul is the lord who is सर्वज्ञः (omniscient) & एकः (singular). In *caraka samhita*, it is described that *ParamĀtma* is अनादिः (begin less) & नित्यः (eternal). He is निर्विकारः (devoid of change), निर्गुणः, निष्क्रियः.¹¹

3. *Ṣaḍ dhātuja puruṣa*

The *karmapuruṣa* is also called *shad dhātuja puruṣa*. *Caraka* describes *puruṣa* as *ṣaḍ dhātuja*, a combination of the six elements, i.e, a combination of five *mahābhūtas* and consciousness, is called *shad dhātuja puruṣa*.¹² This combination of six elements comes under the preview of the science of medicine. The same idea of a person with six components is expressed in *Śusruta Samhita* too.¹³ *Caraka* further explains that like *puruṣa* the diseases are also *shad dhātujas*, i.e., formed from *shad dhātus*.¹⁴

4. *Ekadhātuja puruṣa*

According to *caraka*, the element consciousness (*cetana*) alone is considered as *puruṣa*. This is called *ekadhātuja puruṣa*. In simple terms, the *cetana dhātu* embedded or lodged in the *śarīra* is simply called *ekadhātuja puruṣa*.¹⁵

5. *Rāśi puruṣa/ chaturvimsatika puruṣa*

Caraka samhita defines the *rāśi puruṣa* as the one who bears the combination of *Budhi* (intelligence), *indriya* (faculties), *mana* (mind) and *Artha* (objects). The term *rāśi* means group. Hence the *puruṣa* with 24 factors is termed *rāśi puruṣa*.¹⁶ *Caraka* has clearly explained the 24 factors combined with this *puruṣa*. It is the combination of the Mind, five sensory organs, five motor organs, five sensory subjects and the *Prakṛti* with eight factors.¹⁷ *Caraka* further explains the *rashi puruṣa* originates from *moha* (confusion), *icchā*

10 अनादिः पुरुषो नित्यो विपरीतस्तु हेतुजः । सद्कारणवन्नित्यं दृष्टं हेतुजमन्यथा ॥ (च.शा.१. ५९)

11 निर्विकारः परस्त्वात्मा सत्त्वभूतगुणेन्द्रियैः । चैतन्ये कारणं नित्यो द्रष्टा पश्यति हि क्रियाः ॥ (च.सू.1/56)

12 खादयश्चेतना षष्ठाधातवः पुरुषः स्मृतः (च.शा.1/16)

13 अस्मिञ्छास्त्रे पञ्चमहाभूतशरीरिसमवायः पुरुष इत्युच्यते ।(su.su.1/22)

14 षड्धातुजस्तु पुरुषो, रोगाः षड्धातुजास्तथा । (च.सू.25/15)

15 चेतनाधातुरप्येकः स्मृतः पुरुषसञ्ज्ञकः (च.शा.1/16)

16 बुद्धीन्द्रियमनोर्थानां विद्याद्योगधरं परम् । चतुर्विंशतिको ह्येष राशिः पुरुषसञ्ज्ञकः । (च.शा.1/35)

17 पुनश्च धातुभेदेन चतुर्विंशतिकः स्मृतः । मनो दशेन्द्रियाण्यर्थाः प्रकृतिश्चाष्टधातुकी (च.शा.1/17)

(desire), dweṣa (aversion) and karma (actions of previous life).¹⁸

Proof of the existence of the soul in Ayurveda (आत्मलिङ्गानि)

Thus, the soul is invisible. Charaka provides evidence to support his claim that the soul exists. They are inspiration and expiration, the twinkling of the eye etc, signs and symptoms of living life, the ability to mentally teleport oneself, migration of mind from faculty to faculty, inspiration, controlling mind and indriyas, travel in dreams, death, identification of the object seen with the right eye using the left eye, desire, aversion, pleasure, pain, effort, consciousness, stability, intellect, memory and ego. All these are signs of a living person. These signs are not seen in a dead body. So they are considered as proof of the existence of the soul till the living life.¹⁹ When the jīvātma leaves the body only the five mahābhūtas remain.

Proof of the existence of the soul in Nyāya Philosophy

As per Nyāya Philosophy, the soul is the base of faculties, as faculties are karaṇa (tools) and there should be a kartā (doer) for these tools. The instruments like scissors, knives etc will not work itself. it needs someone (cetana) to operate it. Similarly, the indriyas (tools) will not do their duties without an operator; he is called ātma the doer.

Difference between soul and mind

Caraka and Sankhya's perspectives on the distinction between mind and soul are fairly similar. According to him Mind is active (kriyāvān) but devoid of consciousness (acetana), while the soul is conscious (cetana) but not active (kriyāvān) and is considered a doer, an actor, or an agent of deeds. The mind is not considered as an actor.

Though the ātma is not kriyāvān because of its consciousness (cetanam) it is called kartā. whereas, manas is kriyāvān but due to unconsciousness (acetana) it is not called kartā.²⁰

Qualities or properties of soul

The Tarka śāstra states that 14 gunas are residing in jīvātman²¹. They are Knowledge, Pleasure, Pain, Desire, Aversion, Effort, Number, Dimension, Separateness, Conjunction, Disjunction, Merit and Demerit

According to Śuśruta the ātmaguṇas are Pleasure, Pain, Effort, Respiration, Nutrition, opening of eyes, closing of eyes, Knowledge,

18 पुरुषो राशिः सञ्ज्ञस्तु मोहेच्छाद्वेषकर्मजः (च.शा.1/53)

19 प्राणापानी निमेषाद्या जीवनं मनसो गतिः । इन्द्रियान्तरसञ्चारः प्रेरणं धारणं च यत् ॥७०॥

देशान्तरगतिः स्वप्ने पञ्चत्वग्रहणं तथा । दृष्टस्य दक्षिणेनाक्षणा सव्येनावगमस्तथा ॥७१॥

इच्छा द्वेषः सुखं दुःखं प्रयत्नश्चेतना धृतिः । बुद्धिः स्मृतिरहङ्कारो लिङ्गानि परमात्मनः ॥७२॥ (च.शा.1/70-72)

20. अचेतनं क्रियावच्च मनश्चेतयिता परः । युक्तस्य मनसा तस्य निर्दिश्यन्ते विभोः क्रियाः ॥

चेतनावानु यतश्चात्मा ततः कर्ता निरुच्यते । अचेतनत्वाच्च मनः क्रियावदपि नोच्यते ॥ (च.शा.1/75-76)

21. बुद्ध्यादिषट्कं संख्यादि पञ्चकं भावना तथा धर्माधर्मो गुणा एते आत्मनः स्युः चतुर्दश । (कारिकावली)

Mind, Imagination, Contemplation, Memory, Scientific Knowledge, Decision and Grasping of objects²². According to caraka, there are six gunas in ātma they are - Knowledge, Pleasure, Pain, Desire, Aversion and Effort. These are called Adhyātmagunas.

The size of the Soul

Philosophies have different opinions regarding the size of the Soul. Ayurveda does not much discuss this. The following are the three main arguments on this topic-

1. The ātman is anu-parimāṇa (Minute)
2. The ātman is mahat/madhyama-parimāṇa (Medium size)
3. The ātman is vibhu (Omnipresent.)

Some Upanishads, Budha and Viśiṣṭādvaita philosophies say that jīvātma is Anu. Sankaracharya also accepted this point of view. However, some stated that the size of the soul is medium. According to them the size of the soul in living beings is of the same size as the living being. Many philosophies like Nyāya, Vaiśeṣika, etc. consider the jīvātma to be Omnipresent (Vibhu).

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22. तस्य सुखदुःखे इच्छाद्वेषौ प्रयत्नः प्राणापानावुन्मेषनिमेषौ बुद्धिर्मनः सङ्कल्पो विचारणा स्मृतिर्विज्ञानमध्यवसायो विषयोपलब्धिश्च गुणाः । (su.sa.1/17)